

**Data Processing Report for the
Current- and Pressure-Sensor-Equipped Inverted Echo Sounders (CPIESs)
Deployed in the California Internal Wave Resolving (IWR) Array**

as part of the
National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP)
Global Internal Wave (NGIW) Study
with a SWOT Cal/Val CPIES and a Prelaunch PIES
deployed in support of the
NASA Surface Water Ocean Topography (SWOT) calibration/validation effort

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This report describes the published L3 hourly datasets available here:

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1. Introduction

As part of an Internal Wave Resolving (IWR) Array supported through the National Ocean Partnership Program (NOPP) Global Internal Wave (NGIW) study (Buijsman et al., 2025), eight current- and pressure-sensor equipped inverted echo sounders (CPIESs, **C1-C8**) and one pressure-sensor equipped inverted echo sounder (PIES) with an acoustic modem for near-real-time data transmission (modem-PIES, **C9**) were deployed west of California from September 2023 through October 2024. In addition, the IWR Array included a central full water column mooring (S2). This CA NOPP IWR Array was funded by the US Office of Naval Research (ONR) through the project “A Distributed Network of Internal Wave Resolving Moored Arrays for Assessing Tide-Resolving Model Fields and Improving Forecasts in the Coastal Ocean” (PIs: Amy Waterhouse, Drew Lucas, and Uwe Send from Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO), University of California San Diego; Magdalena Andres and Tom Farrar from Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI); and Jinbo Wang formerly from NASA Jet Propulsion Lab and now with Texas A&M University).

A companion project aims to use the data collected from IWR Arrays and other sources to verify and improve the internal wave predictability in simulations from the global HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) run with tides and realistic atmospheric forcing. That project, also funded by ONR, is “*Diagnosis and Validation of the Time and Spatial Variability of Remotely Generated Internal Waves in Global Ocean Simulations*” (PIs: Maarten Buijsman from University of Southern Mississippi, Brian Arbic, from the University of Michigan, and Jay Shriver from the Naval Research Laboratory, Stennis).

Figure 1. Bathymetry map (shading indicates depth in m) showing locations of the C/PIESs (circles) from the CA NOPP IWR Array (C1-9, yellow), a SWOT Cal/Val CPIES (W1, green) and a SWOT Pre-launch PIES (PL, blue) as well as locations of two full-water column moorings, S1 and S2 (red squares), deployed during the SWOT cal/val period, with a mooring at S2 then remaining in the water throughout the CA NOPP IWR Array deployment period to serve as the central mooring of the IWR Array. S1 was deployed at 31.9155N, 125.0440W (March 3, 2023 – September 17, 2023) and S2 was deployed at 36.1850, 125.1250 (March 3, 2023 – October 28, 2024).

The CA NOPP IWR Array was deployed in the same region where instrumentation for the Surface Water and Ocean Topography (SWOT) calibration/validation (cal/val) program had been deployed previously (Wang et al., 2025). As an add-on to the NASA-funded SWOT cal/val activities, the NGIW program supported deployment of a C/PIES (**W1**) to overlap with the cal/val period when the SWOT satellite passed overhead twice per day (April to July, 2023) and before the full IWR Array was ready for deployment. W1 was deployed from March to September 2023, near the site of the S1 SWOT cal/val full water depth mooring (deployed by SIO) and near the same site where C8 was eventually located when the full IWR Array was installed.

Even earlier, as part of prelaunch SWOT *in situ* cal/val tests, a PIES (designated here as **PL**) was deployed in the crossover region from September 2019 through January 2020 (Wang et al., 2022). A separately generated Level 2 form of these data is already published (SWOT pre-launch field campaign, 2022), but the data are reconsidered and reprocessed here so that the processing steps for the various C/PIES records that have been collected in the SWOT cal/val region west of California are uniform. PL was deployed near a SIO prelaunch mooring comprising a wirewalker in the upper 500 m (<https://doi.org/10.5067/SWTPR-WW001>) and fixed-depth CTD measurements below (<https://doi.org/10.5067/SWTPR-CTD01>).

This report describes data records from PIESs and C/PIESs, all deployed within the SWOT crossover region west of California (Figure 1 and Table 1), either as part of the prelaunch campaign (**PL**), the SWOT cal/val period (**W1**), or as part of the full NGIW CA IWR Array (**C1-C9**). The report explains the processing steps used to generate quality-controlled, processed records (“level 2”) from the “as measured” C/PIES data (“level 0”).

The report also presents “level 3” hourly data records derived from the C/PIESs. Steps used to produce level 3 data records and derived products from the L2 processed C/PIES records often rely on auxiliary datasets from the deployment region. Some auxiliary data records relevant for the C/PIESs described here can be accessed through NASA’s Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PODACC, 2025) at <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/cloud-datasets?search=swot%20postlaunch> and <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/cloud-datasets?search=swot%20prelaunch>. These include (1) shipboard CTD and water sample measurements, (2) the full water column central mooring (S2) deployed both as part of the CA NOPP IWR Array and the SWOT cal/val activities, and (3) the S1 mooring deployed during the SWOT cal/val activities.

Table 1. C/PIES site information.

	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°W)	Depth (m) ¹	Mag. Decl. (°E) ²
C1	36.1465	124.8683	4243	13.04
C2	35.9770	124.7188	4245	12.99
C3	35.7735	124.7627	4268	12.95
C4	35.6544	124.9737	4489	12.95
C5	35.6898	125.2237	4563	12.98
C6	35.8599	125.3696	4597	13.04
C7	36.0642	125.3241	4506	13.07
C8	36.1812	125.1119	4460	13.08
C9	35.9039	125.0334	4449	N/A
W1	36.2050	125.1198	4491	13.14
PL	35.8458	125.0492	4471	N/A

¹ From the pressure record average minus atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) converted to depth (note that no drift was removed from the pressure record prior to this calculation).

² From: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml?useFullSite=true> using the IGRF model and deployment mid-points (April 10, 2024 for C1-C8 and July 18, 2023 for W1).

/Users/mandres/Documents/Funded_Projects/ONR_NOPP_NGIW_2022_ONR_UCSD/CA_NOPP_SWOT_and_PRELAUNCH_PIES_locations.xls

2. CPIES and PIES Data Records

2.1 Sensors and Settings

The PIESs and CPIESs collected measures of bottom pressure, bottom temperature, and round-trip surface-to-bottom acoustic travel time (τ) and were equipped with PAROS model 46k pressure sensors. The CPIESs additionally collected measures of horizontal velocities (u , v) and temperatures from an Aanderaa ZPulse Doppler Current Sensor model 4939R tethered 50 m above the seabed.

Instruments' sampling schedules were as follows:

C1-C8 (CA IWR Array CPIESs):

- Acoustic travel time (τ) measurements: 16 pings every 10 minutes ('fast tau' mode).
- Bottom pressure and temperature every 10 minutes.
- Near-bottom currents and temperature every 10 minutes.

C9 (CA IWR Array modem-PIES):

- Acoustic travel time (τ) measurements: 4 pings every 10 minutes (24 pings per hour).
- Bottom pressure and temperature every 10 minutes.

W1 (SWOT Cal/Val CPIES):

- Acoustic travel time (τ) measurements: 16 pings every 10 minutes ('fast tau' mode).
- Bottom pressure and temperature every 10 minutes.
- Near-bottom currents and temperature every 30 minutes.

PL (SWOT Prelaunch PIES):

- Acoustic travel time (τ) measurements: 4 pings every 10 minutes (24 pings per hour).
- Bottom pressure and temperature every 10 minutes.

2.2 Description of the Data Levels

Level 0 (L0): *raw data from the platform, often in format from the manufacturer. Retained as the most fundamental form of the observations but often not used in analysis.* For CPIESs and PIESs, these are the .dat files saved as raw output by the instrument. See the Inverted Echo Sounder User's Manual IES Model 6.2C (Section 4 DATA RECOVERY and ANALYSIS – 4.2.1 File Types) for further details on the data formats.

Level 1 (L1): *initially-processed data, retaining the original sampling scheme (in time-space).* For CPIESs and PIESs, these are the data from the instruments converted from .dat format to .mat format (using IES_GUIDAT2MAT), and include the raw ping data (24 or 96 per hour, as noted in [Section 2.1](#)) for round trip acoustic travel time (τ). See [Appendix A.1](#) for plots and see the Inverted Echo Sounder User's Manual IES Model 6.2C (Section 4 DATA RECOVERY and ANALYSIS – 4.2.1 File Types) for further details on the data formats.

Level 2 (L2): *similar to L1 but with further quality control and processing, and some calibrations applied.* For CPIESs and PIESs, there are three components of L2 data: (1) hourly data records, (2) low pass filtered data records (2-day low pass filtered in this case), and (3) the amplitude and phase of the barotropic tides calculated using the Response Method (Munk and Cartwright, 1966). The processing is done with the University of Rhode Island (URI) codes using IES_GUIDRIVER. This step includes despiking records and in some cases may include identifying and removing a pressure-sensor drift prior to tidal analysis of pressures. See [Appendix A.2](#) for the processing parameters used here and for plots of the output. See the Inverted Echo Sounder Data Processing Manual (Kennelly et al., 2022) for a description of the processing tools and file naming conventions.

Versions (v#): As updates and processing corrections are applied, different versions of the L2 data may be produced. Presently, there are four versions of the L2 data, but only v3 has been “corrected” as described below:

v1 – was a quick check of the hourly and 2-day low pass filtered records from C1-C9 created shortly after instrument recovery; the processing was run with incorrect sign on the clock drift, so the barotropic tide phasing is incorrect. Superseded.

v2 – was reprocessed with correct sign for the clock drifts (negative instead of positive) and with C2 run with no clock drift because of uncertainty in the value. Superseded.

v3 – as in v2, except (a) the observed clock drift for C2 (17.8 minutes late) was used (and gave reasonable phases for the barotropic tides); (b) L0 data (.dat files) from C5 were redownloaded and reprocessed to L2 because the initial download didn’t capture the full current meter record, likely due to a memory card issue or data transfer error; and (c) v3 includes data from the two earlier C/PIES deployments in the region:

W1 Deployed to overlap with the SWOT cal/val period.

PL Deployed during the SWOT prelaunch program (no clock drift was noted for this instrument, so the phasing of the barotropic tide is uncertain).

For each instrument’s L2_v3 pressure record, the tidal identification ([Table 3a](#)) was done (a) without first removing a pressure sensor drift and (b) by using the tidal prediction option of “Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags”. This version is corrected as described below to produce L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED which is then used to generate L3 hourly data (see [Section 3.1](#)) and will be used to derive other L3 products.

Corrected versus Uncorrected L2 Data: “Corrected” L2 data files include both appended data and data corrections. All CPIESs and PIESs records are appended to include (1) latitude, (2) longitude and (3) average depth (calculated from the time-mean pressure record with atmospheric pressure removed, converted to depth). CPIES records are further appended to include (1) local magnetic declination, (2) deep sound speed, and (3) current scale factor correction (for CPIESs only). For CPIESs, near-bottom currents are measured relative to magnetic north not True North, so a correction is applied here to account for the local magnetic declination. The magnetic declination of each CPIES ([Table 1](#)) was determined using each instrument’s coordinates and the IGRF23 model available via the [NOAA Magnetic Field Calculators](#). Magnetic declination varies temporally but is assumed to be uniform in time using the midpoint of the deployments (April 10, 2024 for C1-C8 and July 18, 2023 for W1). Each L2 file contains this magnetic declination angle in degrees east (C#.magnetic_declination, C#|p.magnetic_declination). The measured u and v are renamed $u_{uncorrected}$ and $v_{uncorrected}$ and the magnetic declination is applied to correct the velocities (u , v). An additional correction is applied to account for the deep sound speed which differs from the default used by the current sensor software (1500 m/s). The rotated, unscaled velocities are saved as $u_{unscaled}$, $v_{unscaled}$. The corrected velocities (rotated and scaled) are named u and v . At present, the most up to date “working” L2 dataset is **L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED** and variables are listed in [Table 4](#) (hourly) and [Table 5](#) (2-day low pass filtered).

v4 – A version L2_v4 was created (but not corrected) using 5 lags in the tidal prediction (see [Table 3](#) in Kennelly et al., 2022) for C1-C9 since these instruments were deployed for approximately 13 months. These are presently not to be used as an independent L2 dataset, but the pressure-related records obtained through this processing are appended

to L3 hourly data (see [Section 3.1](#) and [Table 6](#)), and they are reported here in [Table 3b](#). This version is **L2_v4_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED**.

Level 3 (L3): L3 records and derived products may re-grid the L2 data in space and time and may use the L2 data – possibly together with auxiliary datasets – as the basis for deriving variables not directly measured by the instruments. Hourly and 2-day low pass filtered L3 data and products will likely be improved and expanded as analysis progresses and scientific results are published. Presently, only **L3_hourly_v1** records are published (Andres, 2025), produced from L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED with some appended information from L2_v4_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED.

For the hourly C/PIESs records L3 processing includes identifying and removing the barotropic tide’s contribution to the acoustic travel time record (due to changes in path length as the sea surface rises and falls). As noted above, the L3 hourly data were also appended to include pressure-related records obtained through 5-lag tidal processing.

For the 2-day low pass filtered records, L3 processing will include inferring time series of temperature, salinity and density profiles and of time series of steric height from the acoustic travel time measurements.

2.3 L0 to L2 Processing Procedures for CPIES and PIES Data

Processing to get from L0 to “L2 uncorrected” data was carried out according to the procedures described in Kennelly et al. (2022) using the IESpkg4p06 processing codes. (Note, there is a slightly updated set of codes, IESpkg4p07, developed to handle C/PIES data from popup data shuttles (PDSs), but since these updated PDS-ready codes had trouble with the “fast tau mode” option used for the CA NOPP IWR Array CPIESs and the CA SWOT Cal/Val CPIES, we opted to use IESpkg06).

L0.DAT files collected from the instrument were converted to L1 .MAT files using IES_GUIDAT2MAT. The L0_RAW and L1_MAT folders (not published) contain the L0 and L1 files in folders following a naming convention specifying each instrument’s site-ID and IES serial number as follows:

- For the CA NOPP IWR Array: C#_### having # site ID number (1-9) and ### for the CPIES or PIES serial number
- For the CA SWOT Cal/Val CPIES: W1_447
- For the CA SWOT Prelaunch PIES: PL_199

Figures from this L0 to L1 processing step are shown in [Appendix A.1](#) and indicate that the data records are complete except for the beginning of the bottom pressure and bottom temperature records at site C2 (stable records begin on February 4, 2024, 138 days into the deployment). The L0 .dat files from C5 had to be downloaded a second time as the initial download had truncated the current meter data.

The resulting L1 .MAT files were then processed further using IES_GUIDRIVER with instrument-specific settings, such as clock drift, time offset and deployment/recovery dates ([Table 2](#)) to produce hourly and 2-day lowpass filtered L2 uncorrected data. [Appendix A.2](#) shows processing parameters and plots of these L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED data. This processing step can also include removal of pressure sensor drift prior to identification of the barotropic tide signal in the pressure record. *However, we did not identify and remove pressure sensor drifts in this version.* Future versions of the L2 data and of the L3 products may include identification and removal of pressure sensor drifts, possibly using the method of Donohue et al., (2010) in which the dedrifting and “leveling” (a process by which the deep current meter records are used to infer the deep pressure gradients) are done in tandem.

Table 2. Instrument settings and parameters.

	Inst	IES	CM	IES clock	IES clock	offset	Deployment	Deployment	Recovery
	Type	SN	SN	drift ¹ (s)	drift ¹ (min)	(min)	Date	Time (UTC)	Date
C1	CPIES	454	262	-133	-2.22	0	20-Sep-23	3:55	30-Oct-24
C2	CPIES	455	263	-1068	-17.80	0	19-Sep-23	4:55	31-Oct-24
C3	CPIES	456	264	-143	-2.38	0	19-Sep-23	3:17	31-Oct-24
C4	CPIES	457	265	-147	-2.45	0	16-Sep-23	19:54	29-Oct-24
C5	CPIES	458	266	-112	-1.87	0	19-Sep-23	0:10	29-Oct-24
C6	CPIES	459	267	-137	-2.28	0	18-Sep-23	13:46	29-Oct-24
C7	CPIES	460	268	-62	-1.03	0	18-Sep-23	4:49	30-Oct-24
C8	CPIES	461	269	-110	-1.83	0	17-Sep-23	23:36	30-Oct-24
C9	PIES	365	NA	-219	-3.65	5	22-Sep-23	1:55	29-Oct-24
W1	CPIES	447	255	-86	-1.43	0	28-Feb-23	1:25	14-Sep-23
PL	PIES	199	NA	unknown	unknown	0	4-Sep-19	1:39	19-Jan-20

¹ From the C/PIES Recovery Sheets.

Processed L2 files with hourly data are saved under the filenames C#.mat (with # = 1-9 for the CA NOPP IWR Array), W1.mat (for the CA SWOT Cal/Val CPIES) and PL.mat (for the CA SWOT Prelaunch PIES). Two-day low-pass filtered L2 records output by IES_GUIDRIVER are saved as separate files under the filenames C#lp.mat, W1lp.mat and PLlp.mat, with the records subsampled to 0.5 day intervals. The hourly L2 records also include the amplitudes and phases of the barotropic tides for 8 tidal constituents (see [Table 3a](#)).

The outputs from IES_GUIDRIVER are appended and corrected as follows to produce **L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED** data, which are presently the most up to date files to be used for further analysis and L3 processing:

- For C2 and C7, the L2_v3 uncorrected records were hand edited as noted in the [Appendix A.2](#) (to produce step_0 interim records).
- All records were appended to include each instrument’s latitude, longitude, average depth and for the CPIESs magnetic declination angle (to produce step_0 interim records).
- Recent versions of the IES processing code (IESpkg4p06 and p07) automatically calculate a tidal component for each hourly acoustic travel time record that arises due to pathlength changes as the barotropic tide raises and lowers the sea surface (“tau_tide”) and subtract this from the full hourly acoustic travel time record. However, since this code uses a fixed sea water sound speed for all regions (1500 m/s), this calculation may not be accurate enough for studies of internal tides in some locations (or for comparison of the amplitude of the internal tide across strong fronts). Hence, in the corrected L2 data records produced here, this has been added back to the travel time record and the “tidal_tau” variable has been discarded. (Step 1 in the processing codes.) Note that a barotropic tidal contribution to hourly tau records is identified and reported in the L3 data sets, along with residual tau. For this, a region-appropriate depth averaged sound speed is obtained from the S2 mooring (see [Section 3.1](#)).
- CPIESs velocities were corrected by (1) rotating velocities to account for magnetic declination and (2) using a deep sound speed to find a scale factor to correct the reported current meter velocities which use a 1500 m/s sound speed as the default (see pg 46-47 in Kennelly et al, 2022). For the CA NOPP/SWOT region, the time-averaged S2 mooring bottom-most temperature and salinity are used together with each current meter’s pressure (calculated from the instrument’s mean bottom pressure minus the effect from the 50 m cable) and result in corrected currents that are about 2% faster. (Steps 2a and 2b in the processing codes which also includes appending each instrument’s deep sound speed and scale factor.)
- Records were further corrected to replace spikes in the hourly C9 pressure and temperature records around March 12-16, 2024 with nans (step 2-c1 in the processing codes). Additionally,

the C2 hourly and 2-day low pass filtered pressure records had an incorrect record-mean average pressure and a non-zero mean for the pressure anomalies. This was corrected by subtracting 0.1731 dbar from the anomalies and adding it to the mean (step 2-c2 in the processing codes). Pressure and temperature spikes in the hourly PL and W1 records were replaced with nans as were current spikes at the beginning of the hourly C4 and C8 records (step 2-c3 in the processing codes).

2.4 Level 2 Records

2.4.1. Barotropic Tides: Amplitudes and Phases

Table 3a. Amplitudes and phases associated with the barotropic tidal constituents at each CPIES location determined by the Response Method (Munk and Cartwright, 1966), with no pressure record dedrifting applied and with 3 tidal lags. These values are included in the **L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED** hourly records and the **L3_v1_hourly** records.

Tidal Constituent		Site ID										
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	W1	PL
O1	Amp. (dbar)	0.2242	0.2251	0.2234	0.2226	0.2214	0.2223	0.2226	0.2242	0.2233	0.2232	0.2213
	Phase (°)	206.11	205.32	205.49	205.55	206.14	206.49	206.72	206.43	206.52	206.72	206.13
K1	Amp. (dbar)	0.3567	0.3520	0.3555	0.3541	0.3525	0.3540	0.3549	0.3569	0.3510	0.3535	0.3517
	Phase (°)	221.72	221.74	221.09	221.23	221.71	222.05	222.29	222.02	222.36	222.70	221.21
Q1	Amp. (dbar)	0.0387	0.0400	0.0386	0.0385	0.0382	0.0383	0.0383	0.0386	0.0388	0.0384	0.0388
	Phase (°)	203.58	203.31	203.01	202.95	203.77	204.02	204.43	203.98	203.18	203.79	202.52
P1	Amp. (dbar)	0.1173	0.1156	0.1168	0.1164	0.1159	0.1164	0.1167	0.1173	0.1155	0.1163	0.1155
	Phase (°)	220.27	220.19	219.64	219.79	220.26	220.61	220.83	220.57	220.95	221.23	219.92
M2	Amp. (dbar)	0.4496	0.4420	0.4413	0.4347	0.4303	0.4357	0.4400	0.4473	0.4361	0.4458	0.4363
	Phase (°)	188.37	187.22	185.51	185.91	187.23	188.73	189.93	189.56	188.98	190.45	187.35
K2	Amp. (dbar)	0.0281	0.0286	0.0288	0.0279	0.0270	0.0266	0.0265	0.0273	0.0275	0.0269	0.0262
	Phase (°)	180.22	176.67	176.26	175.84	177.20	180.09	181.43	181.34	179.57	181.76	176.97
N2	Amp. (dbar)	0.0983	0.0964	0.0975	0.0956	0.0940	0.0950	0.0957	0.0976	0.0958	0.0980	0.0941
	Phase (°)	161.58	160.11	158.78	158.90	160.15	161.54	162.73	162.46	162.48	162.52	160.36
S2	Amp. (dbar)	0.1135	0.1145	0.1150	0.1119	0.1088	0.1081	0.1081	0.1110	0.1106	0.1094	0.1067
	Phase (°)	187.17	183.92	183.21	183.06	184.54	187.33	188.70	188.48	186.68	189.27	184.56

Table 3b. As in Table 3a, but using 5 lags to calculate the tidal amplitudes and phases for C1-9 because the deployment period was > 1 year. These values are saved in **L2_v4_UNCORRECTED** (unpublished) and have been appended to the published **L3_v1_hourly** records.

Tidal Constituent		Site ID										
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	W1	PL
O1	Amp. (dbar)	0.2237	0.2251	0.2231	0.2219	0.2208	0.2218	0.2221	0.2236	0.2230		
	Phase (°)	206.41	205.42	205.80	205.87	206.41	206.81	206.98	206.78	206.66		
K1	Amp. (dbar)	0.3571	0.3515	0.3560	0.3542	0.3530	0.3542	0.3553	0.3572	0.3517		
	Phase (°)	221.60	221.58	220.94	221.16	221.59	221.92	222.16	221.90	222.04		
Q1	Amp. (dbar)	0.0409	0.0417	0.0410	0.0407	0.0406	0.0406	0.0408	0.0410	0.0411		
	Phase (°)	199.21	201.87	198.63	198.71	198.92	199.37	199.53	199.50	198.61		
P1	Amp. (dbar)	0.1159	0.1130	0.1157	0.1149	0.1146	0.1150	0.1154	0.1160	0.1138		
	Phase (°)	220.00	219.78	219.32	219.50	219.99	220.30	220.56	220.29	220.83		

M2	Amp. (dbar)	0.4479	0.4410	0.4414	0.4347	0.4297	0.4364	0.4392	0.4456	0.4352		
	Phase (°)	188.49	187.32	185.58	186.05	187.46	188.79	190.05	189.68	188.67		
K2	Amp. (dbar)	0.0307	0.0310	0.0316	0.0307	0.0297	0.0294	0.0291	0.0300	0.0301		
	Phase (°)	179.85	176.89	175.93	175.43	176.93	179.65	180.91	180.80	178.91		
N2	Amp. (dbar)	0.1026	0.1010	0.1020	0.1000	0.0983	0.0997	0.1002	0.1019	0.0997		
	Phase (°)	160.31	158.83	157.69	157.83	159.02	160.36	161.51	161.19	160.96		
S2	Amp. (dbar)	0.1113	0.1124	0.1133	0.1104	0.1074	0.1067	0.1063	0.1088	0.1090		
	Phase (°)	187.47	183.95	183.37	183.24	185.02	187.68	188.98	188.75	186.44		

2.4.2. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED: Variables and Units

Table 4. Hourly records (C#.mat, PL.mat, W1.mat)

Field name	Units	Description
amplitude	dbar	Tidal amplitudes of the barotropic tides at each CPIES site
cmtmp	°C	Hourly current meter temperature
cmtmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for cmtmp record
comments		Processing comments
dcs		Current meter serial number
drift	dbar	Pressure sensor drift
driftcoef		Coefficients for equation describing pressure sensor drift
paros		Pressure sensor serial number
phase	°	Tidal amplitudes of the barotropic tides at each CPIES site
prs	dbar	Hourly bottom pressure
prsave	dbar	Time-average bottom pressure
prsdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for for prs record
refvr	year	Reference year
sn		CPIES serial number
tau	s	Hourly acoustic travel time (including the component due to the barotropic
taudd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for hourly tau record
tide	dbar	Hourly pressure signal due to barotropic tides
tmp	°C	Hourly PAROS sensor temperature record
tmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for hourly tmp record
magnetic declination	°E	Magnetic declination*
u	cm/s	Hourly current meter eastward velocity with magnetic declination and deep

v	cm/s	Hourly current meter north-south velocity with magnetic declination and deep
u uncorrected	cm/s	Hourly uncorrected current meter eastward velocity
v uncorrected	cm/s	Hourly uncorrected current meter northward velocity
u_unscaled	cm/s	Hourly rotated and unscaled current meter eastward velocity
v_unscaled	cm/s	Hourly rotated and unscaled current meter northward velocity
uvdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal days for u. v. u uncorrected. v uncorrected. u unscaled. v unscaled
depthave	m	Average bottom depth of CPIES**
lat	°N	CPIES latitude***
lon	°W	CPIES longitude***
deep c	m/s	Deep sound speed by the current sensor head
SF		Scale factor used to correct u_unscaled. v_unscaled to produce u. v

*From: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml?useFullSite=true> using the IGRF model and deployment mid-points (April 10, 2024 for C1-C8 and July 18, 2023 for W1).

**Average depths are calculated from average pressure with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted.

***From the location at which the instrument was deployed at the sea surface and assuming no instrument drift during descent.

Table 5. Two-day low-pass filtered records at 0.5 day increments (C#lp.mat, W1lp.mat, PLlp.mat)

Field name	Units	Description
cmtmp	°C	Current meter temperature record
cmtmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for cmtmp
comments		Processing comments
dcs		Current meter serial number
paros		Pressure sensor serial number
prs	dbar	Bottom pressure record
prsave	dbar	Time-averaged bottom pressure
prydd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for prs record
refyr	year	Reference year
sn		CPIES serial number
tau	s	Acoustic travel time record
taudd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for acoustic travel time record
tmp	°C	PAROS sensor temperature record
tmpdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal date for tmp
magnetic_declination	°E	Magnetic declination*
u	cm/s	Current meter eastward velocity with magnetic declination correction
v	cm/s	Current meter northward velocity with magnetic declination correction
u_uncorrected	cm/s	Uncorrected current meter eastward velocity
v_uncorrected	cm/s	Uncorrected current meter northward velocity

uvdd	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal date for u, v, u_uncorrected, v_uncorrected
depthave	m	Average bottom depth of CPIES**
lat	°N	CPIES latitude***
lon	°W	CPIES longitude***

- * From: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml?useFullSite=true> using the IGRF model and deployment mid-points (April 10, 2024 for C1-C8 and July 18, 2023 for W1).
- ** Average depths are calculated from average pressure with atmospheric pressure (10.13 dbar) subtracted.
- *** From the location at which the instrument was deployed at the sea surface and assuming no instrument drift during descent.

2.4.3. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Acoustic Travel Time Records

Figure 2. Processed (L2) acoustic travel time records. Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red). Hourly records retain a contribution from the barotropic tide's effect on sea level (this is removed in the L3_v1_hourly records). *continued...*

Figure 2.....continued

continued...

Figure 2.....continued

2.4.4. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Detided Pressure Records (detided not dedrifted)

Figure 3. Processed (L2) bottom pressure. Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red) pressures . Records have been detided using the Response Method, but no drift has been removed. *continued...*

Figure 3. ...continued

...continued

Figure 3. ...continued

2.4.5. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Bottom Temperature Records (from PAROS pressure sensor)

Figure 4. Processed (L2) bottom temperature from the PAROS sensor (which is in the glass housing). Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red) temperatures.

continued...

Figure 4. ...continued

continued...

Figure 4. ...continued

2.4.6. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED Near-bottom Temperature Records

Figure 5. Processed (L2) near-bottom temperatures from the Aanderaa current sensor (which is tethered 50 m above bottom). Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red) temperatures. There are no records for C9 and PL which are PIESSs rather than CPIESSs. *continued...*

Figure 5. ...continued

2.4.7. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Near-bottom Currents

2.4.7.1. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Eastward Currents (u)

Figure 6. Processed (L2) near-bottom eastward currents (from the Aanderaa current sensor tethered 50 m above bottom). Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red) currents. There are no records for C9 and PL which are PIESSs rather than CPIESSs. *continued...*

Figure 6. ...continued

2.4.7.2. L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED - Northward Currents (v)

Figure 7. Processed (L2) near-bottom northward currents (from the Aanderaa current sensor tethered 50 m above bottom). Time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low-pass filtered (red) currents. There are no records for C9 and PL which are PIESSs rather than CPIESSs.

continued...

Figure 7. ...continued

3. Level 3 Data and Products

As described in [Section 2.2](#), L3 data and L3 derived products include variables not directly measured by the instruments. Hourly and 2-day low pass filtered L3 data and products will likely be improved and expanded as analysis progresses and scientific results are published.

As noted, only **L3_hourly_v1** records have been published (Andres, 2025). These are produced from `L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED` records with some appended information from `L2_v4_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED`, as described below. To facilitate analysis of the internal tide measured by the C/PIESs, the L3 processing of the hourly data includes identifying and removing the barotropic tide's contribution to the acoustic travel time record due to changes in path length as the sea surface rises and falls (see below). This leaves a residual acoustic travel time records that contains the internal tide signal (e.g. [Figure 8](#)).

Figure 8. Residual (i.e., barotropic tide effect removed) hourly acoustic travel time anomalies (with the record-means removed) for the IWR Array C/PIESs (C1-C9) for a 10-day period to highlight the semidiurnal internal tide signals.

To produce the hourly L3 data set described below, temperature and salinity profiles measured by the S2 mooring are used as reported in the level 3, version 2 records (SWOT, 2025) in file 'NOPP-GIW_L3_MOORING-S2-AND-CA1_MERGED_START20230303_END20241028_DM_VER02.nc'.

To examine mesoscale processes in and around the California IWR Array and to quantify changes in the background stratification experienced by the regional internal wave field (including the internal tides), low pass filtered L3 products will be produced from the 2-day low pass filtered L2 records (`L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED`). Processing will include inferring time series of temperature, salinity and density profiles and of time series of steric height from the C/PIESs' acoustic travel time (τ) measurements using a region-specific gravest empirical mode (GEM) lookup table (e.g., Watts et al., 2001) by capitalizing on the S1 and S2 mooring records. Processing may also include identification and removal

of pressure sensor drifts (e.g., Watts and Kontoyiannis, 1990), possibly using the “leveling” method of Donohue et al. (2010). This work is ongoing and will be described elsewhere.

3.1 Level 3 Hourly Data Records.

The hourly L2 records listed in Table 4 are appended to include several sets of variables related to pressure and decomposition of the travel time record into barotropic and residual contributions (Table 6).

Table 6. Additional variables included in the L3 hourly records (see also Table 4).

Field name	Units	Description
C_ave	m/s	Vertically-averaged sound speed calculated from the time average of the S2 mooring temperature and salinity profiles. (= 1497.3 m/s)
tau_BT_tide	s	Hourly acoustic travel time at all C/PIES sites (C1-C9, PL, W1) due to the rise and fall of the sea surface from the barotropic tides
tau_residual	s	Hourly acoustic travel time at all C/PIES sites (C1-C9, PL, W1) with the effect of the rise and fall of the sea surface due to the barotropic tide removed (but the internal tide retained).
amplitude_5lag	dbar	Amplitudes of the barotropic tides (calculated with 5 lags) at C/PIES sites C1-C9
phase_5lag	°	Phases of the barotropic tides (calculated with 5 lags) at C/PIES sites C1-C9
prs_5lag	dbar	Hourly bottom pressure at C/PIES sites C1-C9 with the effect from the barotropic tide (calculated with 5 lags) removed.
tide_5lag	dbar	Hourly pressure signal due to barotropic tide (calculated with 5 lags) at C/PIES sites C1-C9s
prsave_5lag	dbar	Time-average bottom pressure at C/PIES sites C1-C9
prsdd_5lag	days from 01/01/2023	Decimal day for prs record at C/PIES sites C1-C9
tau_BT_tide_5lag	s	Hourly acoustic travel time at C/PIES sites C1-C9 due to the rise and fall of the sea surface from the barotropic sites (calculated with 5 lags)
tau_residual_5lag	s	Hourly acoustic travel time at all C/PIES sites (C1-C9, PL, W1) with the effect of the rise and fall of the sea surface due to the barotropic tide (calculated with 5 lags) removed (but the internal tide retained).

These .mat files are created with create_L3_hourly_records.m in /ONR_NOPP_NGIW_2022_ONR_UCSD/California_NOPP/CPIES_data_processing/L3_DATA_AND_PRODUCTS.

All the hourly records (C1-C9, PL, W1) are appended to include variables related to the decomposition of the full acoustic travel time records (e.g., C1.tau) into the component related to the rise and fall of the sea surface due to the barotropic tide (e.g., C1.tau_BT_tide) and a residual (e.g. C1.tau_residual) where any remaining variability at tidal frequencies likely is related to the internal tide (as in Andres et al., 2020). To do this, a vertically-averaged sound speed is derived from the temperature and salinity profiles measured at S2. Using the S2 time series of property profiles, the time average of the vertically-averaged sound speed from the region is calculated, c_ave. The S2 records give a value of c_ave = 1497.3 m/s and this value is used with each of the records (C1-C9, PL, W1).

The (barotropic) tidal pressure record from each site (e.g., C1.tide) is converted to a tidal sea level record, BT_sea_level which is then divided by c_ave to determine the barotropic tide’s contribution to acoustic travel time:

$$C1.tau_BT_tide = BT_sea_level / c_ave$$

(where the pressure record is first interpolated to the time base of travel time record, e.g., C1.taudd). The residual is a “detided” travel time record (i.e., it still contains the contribution from the internal tide but the barotropic tide’s effect is removed):

$$C1.tau_residual = C1.tau - C1.tau_BT_tide$$

The full and residual acoustic travel time records are shown in [Figure 9](#).

For C1-C9 the pressure records were reprocessed to find the barotropic tide using the tidal prediction option of 5 lags (rather than 3 lags) reported in L2_v4_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED (see [Section 2.2](#)). This resulted in slightly different phases and amplitudes for the barotropic tide (see [Table 3a](#) and [b](#)) and tiny changes in the variance captured in the barotropic tide time series and in the detided pressure records (and very tiny changes in the resulting “residual tau” calculated, see above). Thus the “5-lag” tides are not used here for creating further L3 data and products, but the “5-lag” tides are nevertheless appended to the L3 records (as described in [Table 6](#)) in case there is future interest in analysis and processing, particularly for examining whether or not there is a bottom pressure signal related to the internal tide. In that case it might be better to examine `C#.prs_5lag`; `C#.prsdd_5lag` instead of `C#.prs`; `C#.prsdd`. It might also be useful to use harmonic analysis rather than the Response Method (Munk and Cartright, 1966) to detide the full pressure records (`C#.prs+C#.tide`). The expression of the internal tide in the bottom pressure records remains to be explored further.

3.1.1. L3_hourly_v1 Acoustic Travel Times

Figure 9. L3_hourly_v1 records of the full (blue) and residual (red) acoustic travel time anomalies (with the record-means removed).

continued...

Figure 9. ...continued

continued...

Figure 9. ...continued

4. References

- Andres, M. 2025. National Ocean Partnership Program Global Internal Wave Study: California Internal Wave Resolving Array - L3 Hourly CPIES Data (Version 1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17211193>
- Andres, M., R.C. Musgrave, D.L. Rudnick, K.L. Zeiden, T. Peacock, and J.-H. Park, 2020. On the predictability of SSH around Palau. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 50, 3267-3294, doi:10.1175/JPO-D-19-0310.1
- Buijsman, M., A. Waterhouse, and Coauthors. 2025. A multi-agency experiment on internal wave energy, mixing, and interactions and their representation in global ocean models and operational forecasts. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*. In press.
- Donohue, K.A., D.R. Watts, K.L. Tracey, A.D. Greene, and M. Kennelly, 2010. Mapping Circulation in the Kuroshio Extension with an Array of Current and Pressure Recording Inverted Echo Sounders. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 27, 507–527, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JTECHO686.1>
- Kennelly, M.A., K.L. Tracey, K.A. Donohue, and D.R. Watts, 2022. PIES and CPIES data processing manual. Physical Oceanography Technical Reports. Paper 38, University of Rhode Island.
- Munk, W., and D.E. Cartwright, 1966. Tidal spectroscopy and prediction *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 259 533–581 <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.1966.0024>
- Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PODACC), 2025. Website: <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/>. Last accessed Sept. 9, 2025.
- SWOT pre-launch field campaign, 2022. GPS sea surface height, Conductivity, Temperature and Depth (CTD) data from the 2019-2020 SWOT pre-launch field campaign. Ver. 1.0. PO.DAAC, CA, USA. Dataset accessed [2025-09-09] at <https://doi.org/10.5067/SWTPR-PIES1>
- SWOT, 2025. SWOT Postlaunch Oceanography Field Campaign L3 Moorings. Ver. 1. PO.DAAC, CA, USA. accessed [2025-09-20] at [10.5067/SWTPO-MOOR3](https://doi.org/10.5067/SWTPO-MOOR3)
- Wang, J., and Coauthors, 2022. On the Development of SWOT In Situ Calibration/Validation for Short-Wavelength Ocean Topography *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 39, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1175/jtech-d-21-0039.1>
- Wang, J., A.J. Lucas, S. Stalin, M. Lankhorst, U. Send, O. Schofield, et al., 2025. SWOT mission validation of sea surface height measurements at sub-100 km scales. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 52, e2025GL114936. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025GL114936>
- Watts, D.R., and H. Kontoyiannis, 1990. Deep-ocean bottom pressure measurement: drift removal and performance. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 7, 296–306.
- Watts, D.R., C. Sun, S. Rintoul, 2001. A two-dimensional gravest empirical mode determined from hydrographic observations in the Subantarctic Front. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 31 2186–2209

Appendix A.1. CPIES and PIES L1 Data: Processing and Deployment Notes

As noted in Section 2.3, data files were processed from L0 to L1 using IES_GUIDAT2MAT.m from IESpkg06 using the parameters as shown in Figure A.1.1. and Figure A.1.2.

The screenshot shows the IES_GUIDAT2MAT GUI with the following parameters:

- IES serial number and file index: 454_1
- Model: IES62C3
- Raw DAT file Directory: indres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C1_SN_454
- Write MAT file Directory: /Users/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT
- Variables to process and plot:
 - Travel time: (selected)
 - Pressure: (selected)
 - Temperature: (selected)
 - Engineering: (selected)
- Pings per hour: 24 (radio), 96 (radio, selected)
- DCS Model 3820R:
 - Currents: u,v components: (not selected)
 - Data variables: (not selected)
 - Performance variables: (not selected)
- DCS Model 4930R:
 - Currents: u,v components: (selected)
 - Data variables: (selected)
 - Performance variables: (selected)
- Raw Data:
 - Counts: Pressure and Temperature: (selected)
 - Frequency: Pressure and Temperature: (not selected)
- Status: FINISHED
- Buttons: Initialize, Begin File Conversions, Save plot files, Close plots, Reset GUI to Default, Quit
- File format: eps (radio), pdf (radio, selected), png (radio)

Figure A.1.1 Example processing parameters used with IES_DAT2MAT for IES SN 451 and as used for the CPIESs at sites C1-C8 and W1. (See Figure A.1.2 for the parameters used for C9, which was a modem PIES, and PL, which was a PIES, and which both had slightly different settings: 24 pings per hour and no DCS selected.)

C1: IES SN: 454; CM 262

C1: IES SN: 454; CM 262 (cont.)

C2: IES SN: 455; CM: 263

C2: IES SN: 455; CM: 263 (cont.)

Notes about the deployment:

- Pressure and temperature have a gap and noise in the first part of the record. Continuous record starts after Feb 2, 2024 (decimal day 402) though data aren't stable until approximately Feb 5, 2024 (decimal day 405).
- There is moisture in the sphere that may be seawater or oil from the pressure sensor.
- The clock drift determined on deck (by comparing IES time with UTC using the RS232 cable and motocross software) was about 17.8 minutes which is long compared to other instruments (typically a minute or two over a year), but this drift did give a reasonable phase for the barotropic tide (compared to other instruments in the array).

IES SN 455 after recovery with liquid droplets in the sphere

C3: IES SN: 456; CM: 264

C3: IES SN: 456; CM: 264 (cont.)

C4: IES SN: 457; CM: 265

C4: IES SN: 457; CM: 265 (cont.)

C5: IES SN: 458; CM: 266

C5: IES SN: 458; CM: 266 (cont.)

Notes about the data recovery from the instrument:

- Had to re-download the .dat files (September 2025) because the first download (October 2024) only got current sensor data (u,v, temperature) through about 7000 hours (with data for the last 116 days of the record missing, from July 2, 2024 onwards).

C6: IES SN: 459; CM: 267

C6: IES SN: 459; CM: 267 (cont.)

C7: IES SN: 460; CM: 268

C7: IES SN: 460; CM: 268 (cont.)

C8: IES SN: 461; CM: 269

C8: IES SN: 461; CM: 269 (cont.)

C9: SN: 365; Modem SN: 44644

Figure A.1.2: Processing parameters for IES_DAT2MAT for IES SN 365 at site C9 which was a modem PIES. This site had no current meter and was set to 24 rather than 96 pings per hour.

C9: IES SN: 365; Modem SN: 44644 (cont.)

Notes about the deployment:

- Modem flooded during the deployment period.
- Set to 24 pings per hour (rather than 96).
- This instrument did not have a current sensor

W1: IES SN: 447; CM: 255

This instrument was deployed during the SWOT cal/val period (and was the only 1 of 3 recovered). It was deployed at the site of SIO SWOT cal/val mooring S1 and the eventual location of C8. It was deployed for 198 days from February 28, 2023-Sept 14., 2023. It was turned on during the mobilization and then was pinging on deck until deployment. There is no screen grab of the processing parameters, but they were as for C1-C8 in [Figure A.1.1](#).

W1 (cont.)

PL: IES SN: 199

This instrument was deployed during the SWOT Prelaunch period. It was deployed from September 4, 2019 – Jan 18, 2020. There is no screen grab of the processing parameters, but they were as for C9 in [Figure A.1.2](#).

PL (cont.)

Deployment notes:

- Set to 24 pings per hour (rather than 96).
- This instrument did not have a current sensor

Appendix A.2. CPIES and PIES L2_v3_PROCESSED_AND_UNCORRECTED Data

As noted in Section 2.3, data files were processed from L1 to L2 using IES_GUIDRIVER.m from IESpkg4p06 to produce “uncorrected” data. The following shows the parameters and plots of the L2_v2 UNCORRECTED data and notes some data anomalies in records from C2 and C7 which were “hand edited” as described.

C1

● ● ● IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file 454_1

Initialize

Delete files

Initialization

Site Designator: C1

Launch time: 2023 / 09 / 25 0 : 0

Release time: 2024 / 10 / 27 0 : 0

Clock Drift (minutes) -2.22

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory ers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT/C1_454

Write Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/PROCESSED_v2

Raw DAT file Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C1_SN_454

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

C1 (cont.)

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file 455_1

Initialization

Site Designator: C2 **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2023 / 09 / 25 0 : 0

Release time: 2024 / 10 / 27 0 : 0

Clock Drift (minutes) -17.8

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory ers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT/C2_455

Write Directory ndres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/PROCESSED_v2/C2

Raw DAT file Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C2_SN_455

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

C2 (cont.)

Temperature and pressure records (shown below) have been hand edited to be nans until day 305 to remove spikes in v3_PROCESSED_AND_CORRECTED.

C3 (cont.)

IES serial number and file
457_1

Initialization

Site Designator: C4 **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2023 / 09 / 25 0 : 0

Release time: 2024 / 10 / 27 0 : 0

Clock Drift (minutes) -2.45

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory ers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT/C4_457

Write Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/PROCESSED_v2

Raw DAT file Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C4_SN_457

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

FINISHED

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

C4 (cont.)

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file

Initialization

Site Designator: **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: / / :

Release time: / / :

Clock Drift (minutes)

Time Offset (minutes)

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours)

Read Directory

Write Directory

Raw DAT file Directory

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

C5 (cont.)

Notes:

Both temperature records (below) show a jump down that lasts ~20 days (380-400); there is no corresponding pressure jump indicating the instrument did not get moved.

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file

Initialization

Site Designator: **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: / / :

Release time: / / :

Clock Drift (minutes)

Time Offset (minutes)

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours)

Read Directory

Write Directory

Raw DAT file Directory

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

C6 (cont.)

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file

Initialization

Site Designator:

Launch time: / / :

Release time: / / :

Clock Drift (minutes)

Time Offset (minutes)

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours)

Read Directory

Write Directory

Raw DAT file Directory

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning

Process ALL steps

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

eps pdf png

Notes on corrections:

- Pressure record (see the next page) has a 0.1201 dbar drop in pressure near yearday 353.85 (Dec. 20, 2023). Correct for this by decreasing the first part of the hourly and low passed pressure records and fixing the pressure averages (after running IES_GUIDRIVER).
- Also making corresponding changes in the first part of the hourly and low pass filtered tau records (decrease travel time by 0.1594 ms)
- Also changed the first two hourly u and v records to nans due to erroneously high values.
- For code, see:
/Users/mandres/Documents/Funded_Projects/ONR_NOPP_NGIW_2022_ONR_UCSD/California_NOPP/CPDES_data_processing/fixing_jump_and_first_currents_C7.m

C7 (cont.)

See previous page for notes on the corrections applied.

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file 461_1

Initialization

Site Designator: c8 **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2023 / 09 / 25 0 : 0

Release time: 2024 / 10 / 27 0 : 0

Clock Drift (minutes) -1.83

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory ers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT/C8_461

Write Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/PROCESSED_v2

Raw DAT file Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C8_SN_461

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

FINISHED

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file 365_2

Initialization

Site Designator: C9 **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2023 / 09 / 25 00 : 00

Release time: 2024 / 10 / 27 00 : 00

Clock Drift (minutes) -3.65

Time Offset (minutes) 5

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory ers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/MAT/C9_365

Write Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/PROCESSED_v2

Raw DAT file Directory mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/California_NOPP/RAW/C9_SN_365

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

FINISHED

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

C9 (cont.)

W1 (SWOT cal/val CPIES)

W1 (SWOT cal/val CPIES)

IES serial number and file 447_1

Initialization

Site Designator: W1 **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2023 / 02 / 28 01 : 25

Release time: 2023 / 09 / 14 19 : 58

Clock Drift (minutes) -1.43

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory /Users/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_CalVal/MAT

Write Directory s/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_CalVal/PROCESSED/version_2/W1

Raw DAT file Directory Jsers/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_CalVal/RAW/W1_447

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

W1 (cont.)

PL (SWOT Prelaunch PIES)

● ● ●
IES_GUIDRIVER

IES serial number and file 199_1

Initialization

Site Designator: PL **Initialize** Delete files

Launch time: 2019 / 09 / 04 1 : 39

Release time: 2020 / 01 / 18 17 : 09

Clock Drift (minutes) 0

Time Offset (minutes) 0

Pressure Gap Threshold for Tides (hours) 6

Read Directory /Users/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_prelaunch/MAT

Write Directory s/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_prelaunch/PROCESSED/version_2

Raw DAT file Directory /Users/mandres/Documents/IES_DATA/SWOT_prelaunch/RAW

LOW-PASS FILTERING PARAMETERS

Butterworth Filter Order	2
Cutoff Period (days)	2
Output Time Interval (days)	0.5
Gap Threshold (days)	2

Option Selection

Step 1: Process Record from Beginning ⌵

Process ALL steps ⌵

Travel time Prs/Tmp

Number of pings 24 96

Optional Sensors

DCS u,v,t

Travel Time Processing Method

Quartile ⌵

Tidal Prediction Options

Di, Semi-Di, 3 lags ⌵

Output Time Interval for Prs/Tmp and Optional Sensors

Hourly ⌵

Output Travel Time Interval is Hourly

Processing

Waiting to Begin

Begin Processing

Save plot files

eps pdf png

Close plots

Quit

PL (cont.)

